

OLS MODEL TO TEST THE SIGNIFICANCES OF THE RELATIONSHIPS OF THE SHARE OF BUSINESS IN UZBEKISTAN

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In world practice, it is important to develop targeted strategies aimed at further improving the business environment, implementing active business projects to ensure sustainable economic development, pursuing economic policies that have a positive effect on business development, conducting research aimed at using block chain technology as well as ensuring interest in business development by state and society.

Business plays a distinctive and irreplaceable role in the development of the economy in Uzbekistan. Through developing of these sectors is provided with creating new jobs, increasing productivity and competitiveness, alleviating poverty and achieving societal goals. Uzbek economy operates two types of enterprises, which are large and small enterprises, as well as the activities depend on personal and family labor. The condition to run a business in Uzbekistan has been implemented through the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On family business", “On the introduction of amendments and additions” in the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan, “On guarantees of free entrepreneurial activity “ and they are designed to further facilitate the development of business.

The statistical data has been taken from the official website and reports of The State Committee of Uzbekistan. All used data in this article describe the share of business in GDP, in the number of employed, in the volume of production of agricultural products and exports of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

In readiness of this article there have been extensively used methods of observation, collection of statistical data, classification, tabulation; and also diagrams and graphs frequently used in presenting data, dynamic changes, comparison and prognosis of indicators of the development of business.

Descriptive statistics

As the matter of fact, according to the governmental report, the GDP of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2019 in current prices amounted to 249136.4 billion sums and grew by 5.3% relative to the corresponding period of 2016. The index-deflator of GDP in relation to the prices of 2018 amounted to 118.9%.

At the end of 2019, GDP per capita amounted to 7.092 million sums, which is 3.6% more than last year. The largest contribution to GDP growth was made by the services sector, which grew by 6.9% compared to the previous year. Of this, trade, including accommodation and food services, grew by 3.9% , transportation and storage, information and communication – by 8.9% and other services – by 7.3% .

The added value of the industry showed an increase of 4.6%, which was 26.7% in the GDP structure. A positive contribution to GDP growth from industrial production is estimated at 1.1 pp. Growth in the industry as a whole is ensured by the growth of the added value of the mining industry and quarrying (114.6%) and manufacturing (102.8%).

As a result of ongoing large-scale construction of multi-apartment residential buildings, individual housing for standard projects, engineering and transport

communications, social infrastructure facilities, etc., the increase in the volume of construction work was 5.6%. In the structure of GDP, the share of construction amounted to 6.8%. A positive contribution to GDP growth from the construction sector is estimated at 0.4 pp.

The main aim of this paper is create appropriate model and explain the meaning of the relationships. In this way taking into account specific features of our country I prefer to present two models. The former is ordinary least squares model, the latter is analytical method to prognosis for perspective data.

Source	SS	df	MS			
Model	1381.40638	2	690.703189	Number of obs =	17	
Residual	60.0089163	14	4.28635116	F(2, 14) =	161.14	
				Prob > F =	0.0000	
				R-squared =	0.9584	
				Adj R-squared =	0.9524	
Total	1441.41529	16	90.0884559	Root MSE =	2.0704	

A	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]	
B	.7053432	.0788269	8.95	0.000	.5362764	.87441
D	.3849834	.1106778	3.48	0.004	.1476031	.6223637
_cons	-7.808183	4.328464	-1.80	0.093	-17.09181	1.475449

Table 1. OLS regression results of the model for the development of business in Uzbekistan. Note: The results are calculated with STATA 13.

From this Table 1 we can see that all regression coefficients are statistically significant, except the share of business in the volume of production of agricultural products. In further we use analytical method in dynamic lines to predict future events.

OLS model is also found appropriate to the business development in Uzbekistan. Here to change the share of business in GDP, the share of business in the number of employed, in the volume of production of agricultural products and exports are affected.

In order to develop and build model I have used data from 2000 – 2018. is dependent variable, and are independent. In this research it is considered to determine the impact of Business in Industry, Business in Construction, Business in Investment on Business in GDP.

Table 3. Chosen data for analyse and build model.

s	f business in GDP (%)	f business in try (%)	e of business in ruction (%)	of business in ment (%)
31	2,9	38,4	15,4	
33,8	2,5	40,4	13,4	
34,6	5,4	42	16,3	
35	0,8	39,9	15	
35,6	11	49,6	18,8	
38,2	10	50,9	24	
42,1	0,9	52,1	26,5	
45,7	3,2	55,4	23,7	
48,2	4,6	58,4	24,6	
50,1	7,9	42,4	23,7	
52,5	6,6	52,5	28,5	
54	8,6	67,6	31,9	

54,6	9,7	70	35,3
55,8	33	70,6	32,7
56,1	6,8	69,5	35,4
54,5	0,6	66,7	35,8
57,3	5,3	66,9	37
54,9	1,2	64,8	34,8
59,4	4,7	66,6	34,9

Correlation Coefficients, using the observations 2000 - 2018
 5% critical value (two-tailed) = 0.4555 for n = 19

ation

	ness in DP	ness in Industry	ness in Construction	ness in Investment
ness in DP	1			
ness in Industry	5618648	1		
ness in Construction	0139407	8000054	1	
ness in Investment	4115865	9911685	6884958	1

Summary statistics, using the observations 2000 – 2018, we can see here there were positive strong relationship between all variables. Moreover, It is measured descriptive statistics below with the help of Gretl:

	Mean	Median	Minimum	Maximum
The_share_of_bu	47.021	50.100	31.000	59.400
The_shaa	23.458	17.900	10.000	45.300
The_shab	56.037	55.400	38.400	70.600
The_shac	26.721	26.500	13.400	37.000

	Std. Dev.	C.V.	Skewness	Ex. Kurtosis
The_share_of_bu	9.5682	0.20349	-0.39671	-1.4201
The_shaa	12.297	0.52420	0.39220	-1.3893
The_shab	11.650	0.20789	-0.18644	-1.4733
The_shac	8.0948	0.30294	-0.27832	-1.3262

Test for normality of time:

So here test for normality is also good because all results higher from 5 %:

Doornik-Hansen test = 1.36818, with p-value 0.50455, Shapiro-Wilk W = 0.960871, with p-value 0.589652

Lilliefors test = 0.0771912, with p-value ~ = 1,

Jarque-Bera test = 1.1527, with p-value 0.561945

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gretl: model 1
File Edit Tests Save Graphs Analysis LaTeX
Model 1: OLS, using observations 2000-2018 (T = 19)
Dependent variable: The_share_of_bu

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            coefficient      std. error      t-ratio      p-value
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const      18.5884           4.99391       3.722       0.0020 ***
The_shaa   0.0845500           0.138243       0.6116      0.5500
The_shab  -0.0175297           0.198296      -0.08840     0.9307
The_shac   1.02659              0.353880       2.901       0.0110 **

Mean dependent var    47.02105      S.D. dependent var    9.568210
Sum squared resid    174.4283      S.E. of regression    3.410067
R-squared             0.894152      Adjusted R-squared    0.872982
F(3, 15)             42.23750      P-value(F)            1.49e-07
Log-likelihood        -48.02204      Akaike criterion      104.0441
Schwarz criterion     107.8218      Hannan-Quinn          104.6834
rho                   0.454330      Durbin-Watson         1.002461

Excluding the constant, p-value was highest for variable 3 (The_shab)
    
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When there are several independent variables, you can extend the simple linear regression model of Equation by assuming a linear relationship between each independent variable and the dependent variable as follows:

Multiple Regression Model with Two Independent Variables

$$Y_i = b_0 + b_1X_{1i} + b_2X_{2i} + b_3X_{3i} + e_i$$

where

b_0 = intercept

b_1 = slope of Y with variable X_1 , holding variable X_2 constant

b_2 = slope of Y with variable X_2 , holding variable X_1 constant

b_3 = slope of Y with variable X_3 , holding variable X_1 and X_2 are constant

e_i = random error in Y for observation i

The computed values of the three regression coefficients are

$$b_0 = 18,5 \quad b_1 = 0,08 \quad b_2 = -0,02 \quad b_3 = 1,03$$

Therefore, the multiple regression equation is

$$Y_{ni} = 18,5 - 0,08 X_{1i} - 0,02 X_{2i} + 1,03 X_{3i} + e$$

Where

Y_{ni} = predicted income for user i

X_{1i} = number of active Users for user i

X_{2i} = Operating Expenses for user i

Регрессионная статистика	
коэффициент R	0,945596053
коэффициент R-квадрат	0,894151896
стандартная ошибка	3,410066633
число наблюдений	19

	df	SS	MS	F	численность F
	3	1473,483262	491,1610875	2,23750166	1,4907
	15	174,4283166	11,62855444		
	18	1647,911579			

Coefficient of Multiple Determination

The coefficient of multiple determination ($r^2 = 0,894151896$) indicates that 89.4% is so positive.

3. Heteroscedasticity there is no, because we use time series data.

The result of the Autocorrelation means there is no Autocorrelation. In this case, the null hypothesis of no autocorrelation cannot be rejected.

Conclusion

Business more flexible and can adapt quickly to changes in demand, the situation on the global and regional markets, timely respond to their challenges, because it's compact in form, has a mobility and speed in decision-making and it's receptive to innovation. Creating and develop business do not require large expenditures and capital investments, which allows faster and easier to carry out modernization, technical and technological equipment, develop new products, constantly updating its range and provide competitiveness. The higher stability of this sector compared with large enterprises to the challenges and consequences of the global financial and economic crisis. Business are not only a source of income, but also opportunity to disclosure the creative and intellectual abilities of people. This scope allows everyone to show their individual talents and capabilities, thereby forming a new layer of people - enthusiastic, enterprising and prone to self-employment who can achieve the goal.

The most important document accepted by the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan jointly with the Association of Banks of Uzbekistan, commercial banks and international financial institutions is the development of foreign funds and banks, proposals for the creation of the Guarantee Fund. It provides for business the need for the part uncovered collateral for loans of commercial banks issued for the purchase of new equipment.

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Opportunities of various strata of the population in taking advantage of benefits of economic growth also directly depend on infrastructure conditions. Infrastructure services are not only the major consumer benefits but also are means for increase of labour productivity and improvement of market access. Both functions of infrastructure - support of economic growth and expansion of its facilities- has a great importance for overcoming poverty, accumulating human capital, and increasing the welfare of the country.

Taking into account national peculiarities and spiritual values of the republic, entrepreneurship has a special social significance. Social efficiency reflects the degree of achievement of the social dimensions of entrepreneurship. In this case brings to the fore the question of how data with limited resources to best meet the needs of staff entrepreneurial structures (micro level) and all members of society (macro level).

Recommendations will be in the further development of business in Uzbekistan:

- Reduction of government intervention and regulatory authorities in the financial and economic activities of businesses;

- Creation of maximum favorable conditions, privileges and preferences on tax and other payments for business, improvement and standardization of the reporting system and the mechanism of delivery of reports in the financial, tax and statistical authorities;

- Broad involvement and direction for the development of business of foreign investment, especially concessional loans from international financial institutions and private equity;

- Further development of the information management system and advice to business, as well as in matters of training, retraining and skills development;

- Expand opportunities for small businesses bank loans, raw materials.

Needless to say, special initiatives to reduce burdens and support regulatory compliance of business should be balanced against other concerns. Business have been put forward and originally realized in industrially developed countries, but soon was picked up also in developing countries, which have experienced urgent need for expansion and modernization of infrastructure. The most important features are the ability of small businesses to accelerate the development of investment and high turnover of working capital. Another characteristic of this sector is an active innovation and accelerate the development of various sectors of the economy in all sectors of the Uzbek economy.

The inherent flexibility of small businesses and high adaptability to market conditions variability contribute to the stabilization of macro-economic processes in the country. Analysis showed that in Uzbekistan, the sector characterized by a certain yield, high labor intensity, the complexity of the introduction of new technologies, limited own resources, and increased risk of competition. In our view, it is appropriate to establish a definite system which provides for sanctions for clear violations or improper fulfillment of the law. A special role is played in business control over the implementation of legislation and economic reforms should be based on the full legal space. In this case, absolutely equal footing before the courts and arbitration authorities should be all. Uzbekistan has developed industry and regional priority programs and enterprise development are successfully implemented.

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